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RESIST IS DEVELOPING NEW PROTOTYPES FOR CRITICAL HIGHWAY STRUCTURES

RESIST aims to provide a methodology and tools for risk analysis and management for critical highway structures (in the case of bridges and tunnels) that will be applicable to all extreme physical man-made and natural conditions, and cyber-attacks to the associated information systems. The hazards that have been studied are earthquakes, explosions, fires, landslides, floods induced scour at bridge piers and cyber-attacks. Their consequences on loss of lives and injuries as well environmental and economic loss have been identified, evaluated and monetarised. Regarding the risk management, progress has been made on the methodology, which includes calculation of risk reduction, assessment of cost-effectiveness and the break-even frequency that will make the protective measure attractive.

Using as input the extracted technical and user requirements, a concrete system architecture was defined including all the subcomponents of RESIST, which operate either on the inspection field (aerial robotic systems, computer vision systems for defects identification and 3D point cloud creation, as well as onboard inspection sensors and sensor modules mounted by the aerial robotic system on the infrastructure) or the RESIST's system backend (components for structural vulnerability, risk assessment and management, mobility continuity, and cyber-security). The RESIST system architecture will guide the developments of the project throughout its lifecycle.

In detail, the design of the aerial robotic system was developed equipping the different inspection sensors in order to operate in tunnels as well as bridges. Several prototypes have been developed and flight tested, and their results incorporated in the final design. RESIST aerial robotic system comprises of two aerial robots: the visual inspection robot and the contact inspection robot.

- The contact inspection robot is responsible for all the measurements that need physical contact of the sensor with the surface of a bridge or a tunnel, including the ultrasonic sensors and the radiometric sensor. The contact inspection robot will also be in charge of installing the permanent vibration sensor modules on the surface of the bridges and tunnels (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 BridgeContact Inspection robot

- The visual inspection robot's main purpose is to autonomously take pictures of bridges and tunnels with the sensors developed in order to find and classify visual defects (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 Bridge Visual Inspection robot

In order to realize contact width measurements of crack surface opening, a high-resolution measurement system based on ultrasonic waves and a Micro Electro-Mechanical Systems (MEMS) sensor have been designed and developed to be integrated on the aerial robot. The permanent vibration module (installed by the drone on the civil infrastructure) has been also designed to be extremely light, able to measure vibrations with high resolution and assure transmission with low power consumption (Fig. 3-4).

Fig. 3 Prototype of the crack width measurement electronic readout

Fig. 4 First vibration module prototype

The network architecture designed by the consortium was done so in a way to allow for the forwarding of critical messages to operators on the field, to civilians, to first responders and in general with the mind to interconnect the control station of the road operator with all the parties involved on an incident. Additional to the above, the RESIST communication scheme involves a number of redundant communication channels which, with the utilization of REDCOM, can be available under the most unfavourable conditions.

With regards to security, a detailed cyber security analysis has been carried out for the RESIST and pilot assets based on the architecture as well as information received from the pilot owners. The identified threats and risks of this assessment have been collected and mitigation/prevention techniques have been defined. A security assurance model is being developed to exploit in the RESIST assurance platform. The assurance platform leveraged by event captors, will provide real-time security assurance to evaluate continually the security posture of RESIST. To guarantee the security of RESIST, a variety of security controls are currently under development and will be deployed, such as encryption to protect the communication between UAV with Ground Control Station, authentication and authorization mechanisms throughout all RESIST actors assisted with a hardware-key solution and anomaly detection.

In addition, Consortium developed the RESIST app and the mobility continuity module which already provides alternative routes to the users of the application. The module includes the trip scheduler, the traffic simulator, the event management and finally the user management component.

For the integration of all the components of RESIST, a first prototype of the RESIST Integration Environment was developed, a web desktop application to provide a single point of access for all applications of RESIST, including also capabilities like application and user management. Also, in terms of data integration, a platform and an API were developed to gather and store data collected during inspection or shared between the components of the project. An integration architecture was also defined based on the collected hardware and software requirements, and will guide the deployment in the pilots' sites. Finally, two process flow scenarios were presented (one for quick inspection when a quick assessment is required, and one for detailed inspection when a thorough analysis is needed); these scenarios will be also used for the validation during pilots.

An early business plan has been already presented in the first period of the project, which identifies the market size and opportunities, proposes an initial business model based on the business model canvas methodology, presents two indicative business model exam-

ples (one considering the entire RESIST solution as a turnkey product, and the second considering it as a customized service), and finally identifies the innovation results and the potential key exploitable results of the project as they have been identified until the middle of the project. Finally, several standardisation activities have been performed regarding the new European UAS regulation defined by EC.

For practical, security and privacy reasons, it is not possible to work directly on the information system of the highway control centre; therefore it was necessary to start developing a brand new copy with some fundamental variants: the new replica system will receive real data from sensors and cameras, while it will be able to send both real or simulated information, depending on the forthcoming demonstration and other requirements. Specifications to exchange data between A32 Motorway Control Centre and the Resist web platform are still in analysis phase.

When an earthquake, or a structural failure, will be simulated in the Italian Pilot, will be necessary to transmit current traffic conditions data to allow the best possible management of emergency and rescue operations. Remotely Piloted Aircraft System (RPAS) for Inspection will also be tested in a tunnel in absence of GPS signal, while security of communication will be secured by RedComm infrastructure and Wifi network (Fig. 5).

▶ For more information, see www.resistproject.eu/ or contact Project Coordinator Angelos Amditis at a.amditis@iccs.gr

Fig. 5 St. Petronilla Tunnel of the A32 Highway, Italy (in case of emergency)

PARTNERS

